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**The Effect of Language Games on Developing Iranian High School
EFL Learners' Vocabulary Knowledge**

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Abstract

During the time vocabulary learning has always been one of the main concerns for foreign language learners. The present research concentrated on the identification of the impact of language games on developing Iranian high school EFL learners' vocabulary knowledge in Tabriz. To ensure the homogeneity of the learners, before the treatment, an Oxford Placement Test (OPT) was used for the number of 70 students, and after the results 50 students, who were proved to be in pre-intermediate level were selected as a subject for the study. After that they were separated into two groups. The first group was experimental group (n=25) and the other one was control group (n=25). First, the VKS (Vocabulary Knowledge Scale) was administrated to both groups and then 30 out of 50 words were selected as target words. After 10 sessions of treatment to both groups (experimental group through game and control group in traditional way), the posttest with 30 target words was administrated to them. The statistical results of the comparison of the two groups determined that the experimental group performed better than the control group. The findings of this study may have useful implications for teachers, learners, and syllabus designers.

Keywords: *English Games, Word Recognition.*

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Introduction

Vocabulary plays a crucial role in everyday as well as academic communication. Its significance is clear even in the starting phases of foreign language learning process. Language learning is difficult activity. Every instant demands effort, and it must be sustained for an extended length of time. It is common to characterize the process of learning a foreign language as the learner's advancement along the interlanguage continuum from a state of ignorance towards native-like competence without certainly attaining it (Laufer, 1998). Because the number of words each group of foreign language learners and native speakers possesses differs significantly, acquiring vocabulary should comprise a progressive growth in vocabulary size. In this way, one of the fundamental components of language aptitude is vocabulary, which shows how well students can read, write, speak, and listen. One of the most crucial aspects of learning a language is expanding one's vocabulary. Since they must commit new words to memory and learn how to spell them without altering their preferred methods of learning—writing words down, learning by heart, or listening to the teacher explain things—many students find that expanding their vocabulary is tedious. According to Lee (1995), many educators believed that instruction should only take place in a formal setting and that pleasant activities that involve laughing and pleasure are not teaching. Language teachers and academics today hold the view that learning occurs best in relaxed settings, so in order to enhance instruction and learning, teachers must use approaches that have been verified. Using games in learning environments that is deeply rooted in several learning theories (e.g., interactionist's theories, experimental theories) (1938) advocates learning experiences that encourage meaningful learning. Playing games also gives you the chance to use linguistic things repeatedly. Games combine the essential elements of drills with the chance to experience language as a living form of communication by allowing language to express opinions and information. Learning based on mechanical drills is not as effective as learning this way (Laurian-Fitzgerald et al., 2015). Games have a variety of objectives, so they shouldn't just be considered a method to kill time. In addition to its significant value in boosting student engagement and lowering stress levels in the classroom, games also have the benefit of allowing kids to learn without realizing it (Laurian-Fitzgerald et al., 2015). The present study is an attempt to explore whether or not using games in English language classes can significantly improve Iranian EFL learners' vocabulary learning. In many language teaching centers, including Iranian high schools, vocabulary is approached by the current conventional teaching approach, which completely excludes technology and depends on target word repetition that has no meaning and easily translates into the student's native language. This has often caused foreign language learners to treat words superficially and thus forget them quickly. When involved in an act of communication (e.g., speaking or writing), EFL learners often fail to produce sufficient words for effective communication. This is because they have not made use of efficient strategies for retention of words. The researcher, as an experienced secondary school English teacher, has often observed that neither the teacher nor the textbooks provide sufficient conditions for EFL learners to consolidate the words they see or listen. On the other hand, she has observed that whenever she has used something fun (e.g., a piece of art or literature or a game) or a technology, the learners have had positive reactions. Using games is one way to encourage language acquisition, engage students and create a real condition for teaching (Ganbari et al., 2014). Games provide concentrated practice, and, the greatest of all, a

chance for genuine communication. Learning a language is a laborious process, and games support and motivate many students—not just young ones—to stay interested (Rinvolueri, 1984).

The impact of word games on the acquisition and keeping track of vocabulary in EFL learners has been the subject of numerous research studies. According to Rahimi and Sahargand (2008), acquiring vocabulary can be enjoyable. Along with practical methods, engaging exercises for the instructor to lead, and enjoyable games to practice in the teaching environment, they provided some parameters for their work. A different approach is that word games have a beneficial impact on learners' vocabulary expansion, as demonstrated by Alemi (2010). Dolati and Mikaili (2011) state that while employing instructional games can help, teaching a new language to young learners of other languages can be a challenging task. Sorayaie Azar (2012) conducted another study in which he attempted to determine whether and, if so, how games aid vocabulary learning for English language learners. Kabiri (2014) demonstrated how educators can increase motivation and pique students' interests by using games. Additionally, the study demonstrated how teachers can support students in developing self-worth and confidence through the use of suitable games—two crucial components of learning a second language. Akdogan (2017), in a study, tried to investigate developing vocabulary in game activities and game materials.

Using a game in a language teaching and learning activity is fun and amusing and can thus improve the L2 learner's motivation, but the problem here is whether using games in teaching vocabulary to pre-intermediate Iranian EFL can *significantly* help the improvement and consolidation of their learning of new words compared to conventional word teaching commonly practices in Iranian high schools. The aim of this research is thus to compare two groups of Iranian pre-intermediate EFL learners, an experimental group receiving vocabulary instruction accompanied with games, and a control group receiving vocabulary instruction traditionally without using any games. Apparently, using games in a language teaching class can increase the learners' motivation for learning. However, whether or not using games can significantly do better than conventional techniques of word teaching in Iranian high schools has hardly been to put to the test. The results of this investigation can help with theory and practice of language teaching and learning. If the findings show that using games in FL teaching classes can significantly improve Iranian EFL learners' vocabulary knowledge, teachers and syllabus designers need to integrate relevant and well-thought-of games into the syllabus.

Methodology

As previously stated, the goal of this investigation is to determine whether teaching English vocabulary to Iranian EFL learners within the game can outdo teaching within conventional vocabulary teaching. To this end, an experimental group working with the new vocabulary through game was compared with a control group receiving the new words through explanation of words. This chapter deals with the way the experiment was done. It covers the sampling, instrumentation, design and the procedure involved in the study. The participants of the current research were 50 pre-intermediate female students at the age of 13- 14 studying in grade 8 junior secondary school in Tabriz. They were bilinguals of Turkish and Farsi. The participants were chosen on the basis of the results of an Oxford Placement Test (OPT), which identified them as pre-intermediate learners. After then, they were split into two groups at random, an experimental and a control group.

Instruments and Materials

Oxford Placement Test (OPT): This placement test was presented to the classes where the researcher taught to specify their proficiency level. The test had score ranges that identified the proficiency levels from beginners to advanced learners. The students whom the researcher selected were all identified as pre-intermediate learners.

Vocabulary Knowledge Scale (VKS): VKS created by Wesche and Pari Bakht (1996) is used to determine the words foreign language learners do not know before a treatment. To guarantee that the students were not familiar with the new words before the instruction, the researcher selected 50 target words from the student's text book (Prospect 2) and entered them into the VKS. The results showed that 30 words which unfamiliar to the participants, and these words were chosen to be the target words for the treatment.

The posttest: in order to examine the effect of the treatment on the participants, mastery of English vocabulary, a posttest was designed by the researcher. It contained 30 target words taken from 7 lessons of the text book based on the results of the VKS, as was mentioned above.

The treatment took thirteen sessions, with each session lasting for 30 minutes. The researcher took the OPT in order to determine the consistency of the groups. This test was given in the first session of the treatment. 50 learners, whose scores fell within the pre-intermediate score range of the OPT, were chosen as the participants of the research. Following the process of homogenization, the participants were randomized and allocated into two groups: the experimental and control groups. There were 25 learners in each group. In the second session, the VKS was given to the groups to find out whether or not the subjects knew the target words in advance of the treatment. Those target words that were unfamiliar to all the learners (or at least 90% of the learners) were selected for the treatment. The treatment was started from the third session and continued for 10 sessions. For the experimental group, some selected words from their text book was taught. Three words were the focus of attention, each session and the target words were explained through some games. The researcher played four most welcomed games among young Iranian EFL learners which are Word Grap with Songs, Hangman, Charades and Cross Word Puzzles. The games were prepared in advance by the researchers so that the learners would have to employ the lexical elements needed to be practiced and learned. From the third session the researcher asked learners to play Word Grap with songs, this was an extremely exciting game. First the researcher chose a song, which introduced target words. Then wrote every word on a piece of paper, and stuck them on the board. At that time the teacher divided students in to groups and asked them to stand in line in front of the board. Then played a chosen song, the two students should pick up the cards, which heard on the song and went to the back of line the next player did like that, at the end the winner is the group which pick up the most cards. In order to give the students enough time to learn how to spell and comprehend the meaning of the vocabulary words they had studied, the remaining three games were performed following the fifth session. A paper-and-pencil guessing game for two or more players is called Hangman. When one player comes up with a term, the other attempts to predict it by offering potential letters. One of the students was given an assignment by the researcher to think of a word and draw lines on the board corresponding to the amount of letters in that word. For instance, if the student selected the word "chair," she would draw five lines. The other students were asked to guess the word by suggesting letters. If

the suggested letter was in the desired word, it would be written on the line, if not the letter would be written under the lines and the student at the board would draw a part of a stick man's body until it is completed and hanged. The learner who can guess the word sooner is the winner and will choose the next word.

The Charade Game was another teaching tool to teach the vocabularies. This was mostly regarded as reinforcement while the words were introduced previously. The students were in the same groups and were asked to play the guessing game. The teacher gave a brief description of a word or an action and the students gave stripes of sentences. Then, they were supposed to mimic the action or use pantomime to present the word based on the sentences given and the rest guessed what the word or action could be. The team that got the most right answers won the competition and received prizes as well. Crossword puzzles were the third activity used in this study to teach vocabulary. A crossword puzzle typically consists of a square or rectangular grid with squares that have been shaded in black and white. The object of the game is to solve clues that lead to the solutions in order to fill the white squares with letters that form words or sentences. The words or sentences are divided by the shaded squares. The researchers intentionally created the games in advance so that the learners would be forced to utilize the vocabulary words that needed to be learnt and practiced. After the fifth session, the learners participated in these three activities to give them adequate time to practice spelling and comprehend the meaning of the vocabulary words they had covered. Lately she used the fifth session as a quiz session and the tenth session as the review session. In the fifth session the researcher designed a small evaluation test to get informed how the learning process was going on. The learners of the control group were taught traditionally at the other class with the same content. The teaching was teacher – centered with the learners being taught directly by teacher without any technical games. At first, the teacher presented a number of new words and then explained the meanings of those words in Farsi. Then the teacher provided examples in sentence forms (to provide a context) to make the students familiar with meaning of the words. After 10 sessions of treatment of teaching the target words to the learners of the two groups, the posttest was administrated with questions based on VKS results for students to compare the two groups, performances after the treatment. After that, the gathered data were analyzed to examine and compare the effect of these two types of treatment on Iranian EFL learners, vocabulary learning. The study uses a quasi- experimental design with two intact classes. The independent variable is the method of treatment (i.e. teaching vocabulary through the game), and the dependent variable was the students' performance scores on the teacher – made vocabulary tests, that is, the posttest. There was not any pre – test in the study.

Results

Following data collection, the statistical software for social sciences, or SPSS, was used to analyze the data. As previously stated, the goal of the study was to determine whether or not giving a group of Iranian pre-intermediate EFL learners games to use while learning new vocabulary terms may considerably increase their vocabulary acquisition compared to those who do not have such a chance. The results of comparing the posttest performance of the experimental and control groups, who were given different instructions during the treatment, are presented in this chapter.

Before presenting the results, however, it's better to remind the reader of the research question and hypothesis involved in the study.

RQ: Does using language games significantly improve Iranian pre-intermediate EFL learner's vocabulary development?

H0: language games don't significantly improve Iranian pre-intermediate EFL learner's vocabulary development.

In order to make the learners homogeneous in terms of their general knowledge of English before the treatment, an Oxford Placement Test (OPT) was used. The test offered a series of score ranges that identified the test takers' proficiency levels. Most of the learners involved in the study fell within the pre-intermediate proficiency level and those few who were not at this level were excluded.

Also, to make sure that the groups didn't understand the intended words before the treatment, the Vocabulary Knowledge Scale (VKS) was used. Based on the results of the scale, 30 target words which the learners were not familiar with were selected for the posttest.

Following the procedure, the learners in both groups took the posttest to find out whether or not using language games could be a significantly more effective way of teaching new words than the conventional technique. Table 4.1 shows the descriptive statistics of the two groups' performances on the posttest.

Table 4.1. *Descriptive statistics of the groups' performance on the posttest*

Group	N	Min	Max	Mean	Std.Deviation
Control	28	0	30	18.32	10.73
Experimental	31	1	30	26.84	7.47

In order to compare the means of the two groups statistically, inferential statistics must be used, which shows whether the difference between them is significant or not. To compare two independent groups, Independent Samples t-test, which is a parametric test, is used, but before running the t-test, the normality of the distribution of the posttest scores for both groups were checked, as normal distribution of scores is the assumption for using t-test. Table 4.2 shows the test of normality for both control and experimental groups.

Table 4.2. *Test of Normality*

Method	Kolmogorov-Smirnov			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
Control	.202	28	.005	.869	28	.002
Experimental	.420	31	.000	.483	31	.000

As the table shows, the significance values in both Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Shapiro-Wilk tests are less than the alpha level (.05), implying that both groups' scores are *not* normally distributed. If the assumption of normality is violated, t-test cannot be used for comparing two groups, and its equivalent non-parametric test must be used. Thus, Mann Whitney U Test, which is the non-parametric equivalent of Independent Samples t-test, was used to compare the performances of the groups on the posttest. Tables 4.3 and 4.4 show the results of the Mann-Whitney test.

Table 4.3. Ranks

Vocabulary Score method	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks
Control	28	20.45	572.50
Experimental	31	38.63	1197.50
Total	59		

Table 4.4. Test Statistics

Vocabulary score	
Mann-Whitney U	166.500
Wilcoxon W	572.500
Z	-4.193
Asymp. Sig (2-tailed)	.000

As Table 4.4 indicated, the difference between the performance of the experimental group and control group on the posttest is statistically significant at alpha level of .05; $Z = -4.193$, $P = .000$. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Discussion

This study aimed to find out whether teaching new words to Iranian pre-intermediate EFL learners can significantly improve their vocabulary learning. For this purpose, two groups of Iranian pre-intermediate EFL learners receiving different vocabulary instructions were compared. The results of the statistical tests after the treatment showed that the group which was taught by using language games performed significantly better on the posttest than the control group which received traditional instruction by having the new terms translated into the learners' mother tongue,

on the posttest by a significant margin. Numerous other studies' findings (e.g., Alemi, 2010; Dolati & Mikaili, 2011; Mobaslat, 2012; Aslanabidi, 2013; Kabiri, 2014; Lourian & Fitzgerald, 2015) are consistent with the results of this one. The current study's findings, however, are at odds with those of Rohani (2013), who discovered no discernible difference between the experimental group—which was exposed to games—and the control group—which received instruction from textbooks. Her study's findings showed that both groups improved noticeably following the training program and that there was no discernible difference between them. A number of reasons can be given for the superiority of teaching new vocabulary through using language games. Since games are fun and amusing, they reduce stress. A negative relationship has been found between stress and mental functions (Maslach, 1999). Thus, as stress level increases, mental operations tend to be less focused. Games create a happy and enjoyable atmosphere and can thus cause motivation to improve. Research shows that motivation is the key factor of learning, including foreign language learning. Another reason that games can improve learning is that using games in a language class make the learners interact with each other and learn from their peers, and this in turn, reduces the dominance of the teacher. In most traditional language classes, the teacher is the dominant figure who imposes his/her own syllabus on the learner. Learners often find teacher-centered classes boring, impersonal, and stressful, as they have to struggle for grades or pleasing the teacher. Games engage the learners in an enjoyable social interaction, which makes the teacher act more as a facilitator than a teacher. This study searched the relative efficiency of the using games in the improvement of Iranian pre-intermediate EFL learners' vocabulary learning. The study compared the performance of an experimental group receiving vocabulary instruction through a number of language games with that of a control group receiving a conventional vocabulary teaching by explaining the word meanings in the native language. The experimental group greatly outperformed the control group, according to the results. It seems that using games in learning process could be a motivating factor for students in their learning experience and really helpful in learning vocabulary.

The present research study has some implications that are to be taken into consideration by textbook writers, teachers and educators. Teachers should include games in their teachings as they can improve foreign language learners' motivation due to being fun and amusing. Games cause the learners to interact with each other, and such socialization fades the one way and dominant instruction by the teacher, thus reducing their anxiety. Team – working facet of games, according to Ersoz (2000) can promote cooperation and constructs team courage. Curriculum and syllabus designers, too, should use relevant and motivating games in materials and textbooks because games add diversity and variety to learning and make it much more pleasant and enjoyable. This idea has been stated clearly by Richard – Amato (1988).

The following areas might be served as a good motivation for further research. The participants in the present study were all female English learners in one of the high school with the age range of 13-14. Therefore, this study can be extended to other gender, the intermediate and advanced levels, various age groups, even adults and learners with the different educational and linguistic backgrounds. Also a similar study can be conducted in other contexts with a large research samples. The present study is limited to the choice of vocabulary knowledge. Results from the study may not be generalized to other areas of language learning and teaching. Therefore, more research is necessary to see the effectiveness of word games on other skills as well.

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